

Analysis of the Influence of Compensation, Leadership and Work Environment to Employee Job Satisfaction (Studies on Employee Restaurant Fast Serve Mcdonald's in City Banjarmasin)

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ABSTRACT: Study This aim For describe compensation, leadership And work environment on employee job satisfaction at McDonald's restaurants in Banjarmasin City. Examining the influence of compensation, leadership and work environment on job satisfaction employee and analyze variable where between compensation, leadership And environment Work Which influential most dominant to satisfaction Work employee. The research method used is a survey method where The collection of information from respondents was carried out using questionnaires and calculation use program SPSS. Population on study This is employee restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin amount 98 person. Study This use datasubject, namely in the form of written responses from respondents regarding the question items or a statement made into one of each indicator for each variable. For The data source for this research is the primary data source. Based on research results compensation, leadership and work environment have a significant effect on satisfaction McDonald's restaurant employees work in Banjarmasin City. Compensation is in the form of salary provided with fair, leadership Which capable influence subordinate And environment Work which is realized connection with superior in form cooperation Which Good, so can give satisfaction Work form braid Work Which Good with fellow employee. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to can work optimally. This is what makes the work environment have the most influence dominant to satisfaction Work restaurant employees McDonald's in City Banjarmasin.

KEYWORDS: Compensation, leadership, environment Work And satisfaction Work

I. INTRODUCTION

McDonald's is restaurant Ready serve Which sell food Which safe on visitoris a fundamental building block in any business that feeds on people, This is location heart on trust consumer towards the brand (brand) McDonald's. That's why we all work hard every day to put food on the table which is safe for more than 50 million guests in all our restaurants around the world. Follow procedure And standard *food safety* We walk along with serve food quality in environment Which clean. McDonald's vision is to become a fast food restaurant with service best in world. For reach vision McDonald's always ensure quality its products, delivering satisfactory service, offering cleanliness and food product safety and other added values. The consumer's smile is Important things for McDonald's, there are 4 important things that must be done, namely; *service, quality, cleanliness* and *value*. McDonald's mission is to be the best company for all employees in every community around the world. Providing services with system operational Which superior for every consumer in every restaurant branch One of them is McDonald's in the city of Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan . Keep going experience development to direction Which profitable as a brand, as well as continuing to develop McDonald's operational systems in that direction more Good Again through innovation and technology.

Compensation is one of the factors that influences a person's job satisfaction employee. Every organization should endeavor For increase satisfaction Work his employees with give program compensation Which fair And worthy as well as competitive. According to Madurese (2001) And Trisnawati (2017) factors Which can influence satisfaction Work between other program compensation Which fair And worthy, security work, timetable Work Which flexible, quality service And program involvement employee. Satisfaction to compensation determined by justice compensation, compensation levels, and compensation administration practices. Satisfaction to compensation Also related with rotation employee (*turnovers*) And absence (*absenteeism*) . Leadership according to Robbins (1996:4) is process or a series of interconnected activities with others that is move, guide And direct as well as supervise person other in dosomething, either individually or collectively. All these activities are possible called as business influence feeling, thought And Act in demand person other toward achieving a goal, therefore leadership is also an interaction process between leaders and employees to do something in accordance with the goals company. The work environment according to Rivai (2006: 165) is the overall facilities and infrastructure those around employees who are doing the work themselves. Environment

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This work will include the workplace, facilities, work aids, cleanliness, lighting and calm. The work environment is the physical factors that exist around the work Which can influence employee in operate task Which charged to him. Then it can be understood that the work environment has a huge influence on employee habits in carrying out their work. If the work environment is in around good employees, the employees will have high work discipline and in a way direct will intertwined cooperation Which Good in company so that will influential on satisfaction Work employee. If environment Work Which There is in around bad employees, it will lead to low work discipline and therefore satisfaction work will decrease.

With thereby compensation Which fair And in accordance, leadership Which capable move, guide And direct as well as environment Work Which conducive can make employees feel satisfaction at work. Based on the description, it is necessary researched is: "Analyze influence compensation, leadership And environment Work to satisfaction Work employee restaurant McDonald's in the city Banjarmasin".

A. Compensation

Compensation is everything an employee receives in return service For Work or devotion they. In something organization problem compensation is matter Which very complex, However most important for employees as well the organization itself. Providing compensation to employees must have a logical and rational basis. However, there are factors emotional And humanity No can ignored Notoatmodjo (2009:142).

Compensation has a broader meaning than wages or salaries. Wages or wages more emphasize on reply service Which nature financial, whereas compensation covers reply service financial nor non-financial. Compensation is the provision of remuneration, whether in the form of money (financial) nor No direct form award (non-financial) Samsuddin (2006: 187).

Process compensation is something network various sub process Which the complex with Meaning For give reply service to employee in implementation work And For motivating employee so that reach level desired work performance. Compensation includes payment of wages and salaries Handoko (2011:161).

B. Leadership

In something organization, leadership hold role Which important Because leader that's Which will move And direct organization in achieving the goal and at the same time it is not an easy task. No easy, Because must understand every behavior subordinate Which vary. Subordinates are influenced in such a way that they can provide devotion and participation in the organization effectively and efficiently. In other words, that success or not business achievement objective organization determined by quality Sutrisno's leadership (2012:213). Hasibuan (2008 :169) state that leader is somebody Which use authority his leadership, direct his subordinates For do part his job in achievement objective company.

Siagian (2009:62) defines the definition of leadership as following; Leadership as ability And Skills somebody Which occupying positions as work unit leaders to influence behavior other people, especially subordinates, to think and act in such a way so that through behavior Which positive He give contribution real in achievement objective organization.

C. Environment Work

Sihombing (2004) states that: "work environment is a factor outside physique man Good physique nor non physique in something organization. Factor physique This includes work equipment, workplace temperature, tightness and crowding work, noise, work space area while non-physical includes work relations Which formed in agency between superiors And subordinate as well as fellow employee".

Environment Work Which support productivity Work will give rise to job satisfaction for workers in an organization. "Work environment indicators are (1) relationships with superiors, (2) relationships with coworkers, (3) facilities place Work" Sihombing (2004).

D. Satisfaction Work

Discussions about job satisfaction need to be preceded by the assertion that problem satisfaction Work it's not matter simple, Good in meaning the concept nor in meaning the analysis, Because "satisfaction" have connotation Which diverse variety. However, it is still relevant to say that job satisfaction is a person's perspective, both positive and negative nature negative about his job Siagian (2008:295).

According to Handoko (2011:193) "job satisfaction is an emotional state pleasant or No pleasant with where employee looking their work. "Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards work. This can be seen in the positive attitude of employees towards work and everything something which faced in environment it works.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

A. Research Instrument

The data collected in this research includes two types of data, namely primary data And secondary. As for techniques Which used in collection data the is as follows:

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Questionnaire is something list question Which served to respondents to obtain data related to research. this questionnaire intended to obtain primary data. Data obtained using questionnaire Which nature closed that is question Which made like that appearance so that respondents are limited to giving answers to only a few alternatives or in one answer Just Nasir (1988:24) This research uses a questionnaire instrument to obtain data data study. scale measurement Likert. Scale Likert used For measure attitude, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group about social phenomena. With This scale, phenomena specifically defined by the researcher are called variables study.

Instrument study be measured use scale likert with score:

- a. Very Agree (SS) score 5
- b. Agree (S) score 4
- c. Neutral (N) score 3
- d. No Agree (TS) score 2
- e. Very No Agree (STS) score 1

B. Test Validity

Validity is something size Which show levels validity or validity something instrument. Something instrument Which valid or valid have high validity. On the other hand, an instrument that is less valid means it has less validity low Arikunto (2006:168). Test validity instrument done For know how far the research instrument is able to reflect the content in accordance with matters and characteristic Which be measured. It means,

each item of the instrument truly describes the overall content or nature get up the concept that is the basis for preparing the instrument. This test is used formula correlation product moments with number rough Which stated by Arikunto,(2006: 170) like following:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Information:

- rx_y = correlation coefficient of an
- item_n = many data
- X = total score items X
- Y = total score items Y

Test validity is test about ability something questionnaire, so that truly can measure what you want to measure. An instrument is valid if it is able to measure what it is desired and can reveal data from the variables studied appropriately. Tall low validity show so far where data Which collected Nodeviates from the picture of intended validity. If r (correlation), with the item is valid. The amount of r for each question item can be seen from SPSS at Corrected Items Correlation column). Validity test criteria in brief (rule of thumb) is 0.3. If Correlation Already more big from 0.3, question Which made categorized valid or authentic Setiaji (2004:61).

C. Test Reliability

Something questionnaire called reliable or reliable If answers somebody consistent . Setiaji (2004:60) : To test instrument reliability, the Alpha formula is used from Cronbach Omar (2003:106) as follows:

$$r_{11} = \frac{1}{k} \left[1 - \frac{\sum \sigma_i^2}{\sigma_t^2} \right]$$

Information:

- r₁₁ = reliability instrument
- k = many question items or many question
- Σσ_i² = amount variance item
- σ_t² = variance total

An instrument can be said to be reliable if it has a reliability coefficient reliability as big as 0.6 (60%) or more. Arikunto (2006:57)

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determine criteria index reliability.

Table 1. Criteria Index Coefficient Reliability

No.	Intervals	Criteria
1	<0.200	Very Low
2	.200-.399	Low
3	0.400-0599	Enough
4	.600-.799	Tall
5	0,800-1,000	Very Tall

Source data: McD Human Resources Development, 2022

The reliability test used is *Alpha Cronbach*. If alpha is more small from 0.6 so stated No reliable And on the contrary stated reliable. Furthermore, Validity and Reliability testing is carried out with the help of facilities program SPSS version 1 7 for windows.

D. Population and Sample Study

The population is the entire object that is the target of Wahyuni's research (2011:4). Population on study This is all over employee or employee operational restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin has a total of 98 person. With therebytechnique taking sample done with method *census*, Because all over population made respondents in this study .

Table 2. Population on Employee Restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin

No.	Name Restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin	Amount
1	McDonald's Prince Antasari	21
2	McDonald's Partner 1	15
3	McDonald's Kayutang i	35
4	McDonald's Sultan Adam	27
	Amount whole	98

Source data: McD Human Resources Development , 2023

E. Technique Analysis Data

In analyzing research data, statistical calculations are used for testing hypothesis by first processing the data that has been obtained. Based on variables mentioned above, the model that will be used in this research is regression Which shaped regression multiple beneficial For know how much big contribution from every variable Which made as variable because to variable consequences, apart from that we also want to know whether the respondent variables (effects) with variables because is *best linear combination* Which in a way statistics quite meaningful, while the benefits the correlation coefficient itself for know big connection between all variable that observed.

The method used is aimed at testing causal influences between the independent variables (X) in this case compensation, leadership and environment work on the dependent variable (Y) in this case job satisfaction. This analysis is used to determine the influence of more than one independent variable on a variable bound. Meanwhile, a number of other independent variables are suspected to be related with the dependent variable being constant or fixed. This analysis is also useful For know variable where Which most influential between other variables.

III. RESULTS

A. Characteristics Respondent

Respondent in study This is 98 person employee on restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin. Furthermore Can served characteristics respondents according to age, education And long worked as following:

Table 3. Respondent Characteristics Characteristics respondents according to age

No.	Age (year)	Amount	Percentage
1	<30	75	76.53
2	30-39	17	17.34
3	40-49	6	6.13
	Amount	98	100

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Characteristics respondents according to education

No.	Education	Amount	Percentage
1	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	66	67.35
2	Diploma	9	9.19
3	Bachelor	23	23.46
Amount		98	100

Characteristics respondents according to long Work

No.	Long Work (year)	Amount	Percentage
1	<5	25	25.51
2	5-10	41	41.84
3	10-20	32	32.65
Amount		98	100

Source data: McD Human Resources Development, 2023

B. Validity and Reliability

Testing the validity of indicator items can be done using software SPSS. In the test, each item will be tested for its relationship with the total score of the variable intended that is each items Which There is in in variable X And Y tested the relationship with the total score of these variables. Whether an instrument indicator is valid or not can is known with compare coefficient correlation Pearson productmoments with levels significant 95%.

Results test validity is known mark correlation between each items with score total items. This correlation value is compared with the r table. r table is searched at a significance of 0.05 with a 2-sided test and the number of data (n) = 98 or df = 96, then we get an r table of 0.199. For variable Compensation (X 1), Leadership (X 2), Environment Work (X 3) And Job Satisfaction (Y) there is no item that has a value of less than 0.199 so these items stated valid.

Test reliability intended For know exists correlation instrument inits users or with say other tool measuring the have results Which consistent if used many times on time Which different. Testing reliability in study This use method alpha cronbach Whichaim For test instrument Which used. Results testing reliability served in form table as follows:

Table 4. Results Test Reliability

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Information
Compensation (X 1)	0.708	Reliable
Leadership (X 2)	0.716	Reliable
Environment Work (X 3)	0.714	Reliable
Satisfaction Work (Y)	0.704	Reliable

Source data: Data Study processed use SPSS 17

The results of reliability testing can determine the reliability value of the compensation variable, leadership, work environment and job satisfaction above 0.6 then you can concluded that measuring instrument in study this is reliable.

C. Test Hypothesis 1 (test F)

Furthermore done test model with determine big F_{count} with use test F Which intended For know influence variable free (X) simultaneously on the dependent variable (Y), by comparing $F_{calculate}$ with F_{table} , if it meets the requirements, namely $F_{count} > F_{table}$ then hypothesis acceptable. Then see level significance on $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 5. Results Test Hypothesis 1 (test F)

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	314,573	3	104,858	23,032	,000 ^a
	Residual	427,957	94	4,553		
	Total	742,531	97			

Source data: Data Study processed use SPSS 17, 2023

Based on the output of the F test results, it can be seen that the $F_{calculated} = 23.032$ and F_{table} at df 1 = 3 and df 2 = 94 obtained $F_{table} = 2.70$. The $F_{calculated}$ value is greater from the F_{table} , namely $23.032 > 2.70$ at the significant level $\alpha = 5\%$ ($0.000 < 0.005$) which means there is significant influence between compensation, leadership and environmental variables simultaneous work on employee job satisfaction in restaurants McDonald's in the city Banjarmasin.

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Thus hypothesis 1 states that the compensation variable, Leadership and work environment simultaneously influence satisfaction Work restaurant employees McDonald's in the city Banjarmasin was declared acceptable .

D. Test Hypothesis 2 (test t)

Test t intended For know influence variable free (X) in a way Partialon the dependent variable (Y), by comparing the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ with t_{table} , if it meets the requirements, namely $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$ then the hypothesis can be accepted. Then look at the significance level at $\alpha < 0.05$. Formula to search mark $t_{\text{table}} = \text{level trust shared } 2$; amount respondents reduced amount variablefree minus 1 or If written in formula form as follows:

$$t_{\text{table}} = \alpha/2 : nk-1$$

$$t_{\text{table}} = 0.05/2 : 98-3-1t_{\text{table}} = 0.025 : 94$$

Then look for the distribution of t_{table} values and find the t_{table} valuesas big as 1,989.

Table 6. Results Test Hypothesis 2 (test t) Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	13,119	4,276		3,068	,003		
Compensation (X 1)	,256	,098	,224	2,604	.011	,831	1,204
Leadership (X 2)	,309	.124	,235	2,500	.014	,696	1,436
Environment Work (X 3)	,550	.118	,405	4,674	,000	,816	1,226

Source data: Data Study processed use SPSS 17

- 1) The compensation variable (X 1) has a $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value of 2.604 > t_{table} 1.989 and value significance 0.011 < 0.05 so can concluded that Ho rejected And Ha accepted Which This means that compensation (X1) partially has a significant effect on job satisfaction (Y).
- 2) Variable leadership (X 2) own mark t_{count} as big as 2,500 > t_{table} 1,989 And marksignificance 0.014 < 0.05 so can concluded that Ho rejected And Ha accepted Which This means that leadership (X 2) partially has a significant effect on satisfaction work (Y).
- 3) The work environment variable (X 3) has a $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value of 4.674 > t_{table} 1.989 and marksignificance 0,000 < 0.05 so can concluded that Ho rejected And Ha accepted Which It means environment Work (X 3) in a way Partial influential significant to satisfaction Work (Y).

Next, to test hypothesis 2, the work environment variable is a variable which has a more dominant influence on job satisfaction among McDonald's restaurant employees in Banjarmasin City . Based on the analysis shown in the table above for each variable shows the standardized β coefficient with the results of the β coefficient 3 work environment = The largest 0.405 is followed by the β 2 leadership coefficient = 0.235 and finally the β 1 coefficient compensation = 0.224. With thereby variable Which influential most dominant And significantto job satisfaction is the work environment means to improve and shapeJob satisfaction among McDonald's restaurant employees in Banjarmasin City is the most significant is environment Work. With thereby hypothesis 2 Which state that variable environment Work is variable Which influential most dominant to satisfaction Work employeerestaurant McDonald's in Banjarmasin City , declared acceptable .

IV. DISCUSSION RESULTS STUDY

Based on the results of research and hypothesis testing, it can be concluded :

- 1) Based on the results of the analysis of descriptions of compensation, leadership, work environment and satisfaction Work employee restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin , so can explained:
 - a) Based on results analysis description can is known that compensation Which be measured with indicator giving wages, incentive And allowance service. Giving wages is decider compensation for employee restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin . Matter This can used as encouragement For Work is getwages And in McDonald's in City Banjarmasin salary standards more from wages minimum County town (UMK).
 - b) Based on the results of the description analysis, it can be seen that leadership is be measured with indicator influence subordinate And clarity order And task. Clarity of orders and tasks is a determinant of leadership, a leader who is Giving clear instructions to subordinates will make it easier for subordinates in finish order And task employee in accordance with his abilities.
 - c) Based on the results of the description analysis, it can be seen that the work environment is measured by indicators of relationships with superiors, relationships with coworkers And facility place Work connection with superior is decider environment Work. Matter This become decider on employee restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin, there must be cooperation between superiors and subordinates so that SOPs are adhered to, so that guaranteed service, quality and cleanliness.

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Based on the results of the description analysis, it can be seen that job satisfaction is measured with indicators of the job itself, supervision, promotion opportunities and coworkers are a determinant of job satisfaction. This is decisive for intertwine connection Good with colleague Work And accepted colleague Work on employee restaurant McDonald's in the City Banjarmasin .

2) Compensation, leadership And environment Work influential significant to satisfaction Work employee restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin. Compensation form wages given fairly, leadership that is able to influence subordinates and work environment that is realized by relationships with superiors in the form of cooperation good, then it can provide job satisfaction in the form of a good work relationship with fellow employees.

3) Work environment variables have a dominant influence on job satisfaction, environment Work is a place where employees carry out activities every day. Environment Conducive work provides a sense of security and allows employees to be able to work Work optimally . In accordance with need employee that is there is cooperation Which Good Between superiors and subordinates in carrying out work, there is good communication whether with fellow colleagues in the office or in the field, there is equipment good work and functions to support the implementation of tasks, there is a place service for employees like the place worship and good and clean toilets, There are good and comfortable working conditions. This is what makes the environment Work own influence Which most significant to satisfaction Work employee restaurant McDonald's in Banjarmasin City .

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, it shows that the variable compensation, leadership And environment Work in a way simultaneous influential to satisfaction Work employee on restaurant McDonald's in City Poor. Is known that between third variable free Which researched it turns out Correct variable environment

Work Which influential most big to satisfaction Work employee on restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin .

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results analysis and discussion of research results, then they can be taken a number of conclusion as follows:

1. Based on the results of the analysis of the description of the compensation variable (X 1), the leadership variable (X 2), work environment variables (X 3) and job satisfaction variables (Y) for restaurant employees McDonald's in City Banjarmasin , then you can The following conclusions are drawn :

a. Compensation with indicators of salary, incentives and service allowances. Providing salaries is a determinant of compensation for McDonald's restaurant employees in the City Banjarmasin.

b. Leadership with indicators of influencing subordinates, clarity of orders and tasks. Clarity order And task is decider leadership employee restaurant McDonald's in Banjarmasin City.

c. Work environment with indicators of relationships with superiors, relationships with colleagues and workplace facilities. The relationship with superiors is an environmental determinant The work of McDonald's restaurant employees in Banjarmasin City must be collaborative between superior And subordinate.

d. Job satisfaction with indicators of the job itself, supervision, promotion opportunities and coworkers are determinants of job satisfaction. This is decisive to establish good relationships with co-workers and be accepted by co-worker employee restaurant McDonald's in the City Banjarmasin.

2. Compensation, leadership And environment Work influential significant to Job satisfaction of McDonald's restaurant employees in Banjarmasin City. Compensation in the form of salary given fairly, leadership that is able to influence subordinates and work environment that is realized by relationships with superiors in the form of cooperation good, then it can provide job satisfaction in the form of a good work relationship with fellow employees.

3. Variable environment Work influential most dominant to satisfaction Work, The work environment is a place where employees or workers carry out activities every day. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and enables employees to be able to work more optimally. This is what makes the work environment have an influence the most dominant influence on job satisfaction of McDonald's restaurant employees in the city Banjarmasin.

VI. SUGGESTION

Based on on analysis data And discussion need exists effort Formaintained and increase satisfaction Work employees include:

1. Leaders pay more attention to subordinates in terms of welfare and well-being finish difficulty Work Because matter This can add Spirit employee

in work so that work can be carried out optimally in accordance with objective.

2. Increase cooperation Which Good between superior with subordinate in carry out work And establish communication Which Good with fellow colleague Work in office as well as in the field. To be a source of enthusiasm and motivation for employees carrying out tasks and solving problems so that a sense of togetherness grows To use increase optimization satisfaction Work at the restaurant McDonald's in City Banjarmasin.

3. Leader more often give suggestion And insert to employee in carry out their duties due to the level of employee or employee's

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ability to absorb orders nor in finish problem No with each other with Which other.

4. Increasing employee human resources by providing education And training so that created employee Which have expertise in accordance the field with hope become employee professional Which Good, discipline And Honest.
5. Creating policy patterns that regulate compensation and quality leadership and providing a good work environment to employees so that level of satisfaction work that so far this has been achieved maintained and even improved.

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